

Kavur an Iron Age settlement- An Archaeological Site: A Recent Perspective

P.T. Nagarajan

PhD Research Scholar,(Part Time),

Dept. of Sanskrit and Indian Culture,

SCSVMV, Enathur, Kanchipuram-631561.

Abstract— The present paper discusses archaeological investigations carried out in Kavur village, Chengalpattu District, which have revealed findings from the Middle Paleolithic to the historical period of the region. The present paper is a preliminary exploration based on findings ranging from the Middle Paleolithic to the historical period. However, there is a good scope for further investigation in the study area.

Keywords— Kavur, Iron Age, Archaeology, Palar, Chengalpet

I. INTRODUCTION

The archaeology and history of the selected area can be brought to light with the help of material remains collected through scientific methods of Exploration and Excavation. The current exploration in the Lower Palar River Valley aims to attempt an intensive study of material culture right from Prehistory to the Historical period through extensive fieldwork carried out by the present author during exploration conducted by the author on the southern bank of the Palar River for his doctoral research the site Kavur was discovered.

II. PAGE LAYOUT

The Kavur (12°42'55" N. Lat. and 79°56'41" E) is an obscure hamlet situated about 80 (Put km from Chennai and Chengalpet with directions). The approach to this village is (Near By village). The Village can be accessed either by bus or train, and Walajabad is the closest railway station for Kavur. The Palar River flows 2 km south of the village of Kavur. (Fig 1).

Fig 1: Location of Kavur Archaeological Site

The district has a varied range of rock types, mainly charnockites, gneisses, granites, and sedimentary rocks, such as shale, sandstone, and recent alluvium and beach sand along the sea coast. The district has a combination of hard rock and sedimentary formations; hence, the landforms in these formations also vary.

Fig 2: General view of archaeological sounds.

Residual hills are formed by selbergs. Floodplains along the course of the Palar River are hard rock areas. The Kancheepuram district is largely underlined by hard archaean crystalline rocks and, to a smaller extent, sedimentary formations. Pebble beds are observed both in the Palar River and in the paleo channels. These pebble beds are predominantly quartz,

but occasionally, charnockite and gneiss pebbles are also observed. They are well rounded to spherical, sometimes with a clayey matrix.

III. ETYMOLOGY

The village is known as $kav+ur=kavur$, and the suffix *ur* denotes the ancient settlement. Thus, the author attempts to understand the archaeology and history of Kavur through the ages with the help of the materials collected at the site. (Possibly to write epigraphical sources for Ur). The site is in an intact condition with minimum interventions such as a small dig showing the stratigraphic layers of the site, and the rain gully (Fig. 3) shows the wealth of the site in terms of pottery.

Fig 3: On the rain guile, no potsherds were exposed at various time scales, such as Black and Red ware, black ware, dull red ware, and red slipped ware.

IV. PREVIOUS WORK

Chengalpattu District is one of the most important archaeological regions in Tamil Nadu, where numerous archaeological sites have been identified over the past 150 years. The region is particularly known for continued cultural habitation from the Paleolithic to the Historical period. The British Geologist Robert Bruce Foote was the first person to discover that stone tools in the subcontinent were made in Pallavaram back in 1863. In 1916 F.J. Richards and T.N Hearsy from the forest department discovered and excavated the site called

Odugattur located on the banks of Palar, three cairn circles with U- shaped portholes were excavated, which yielded pottery, and a large number of antiquities were collected, namely, iron objects, semi-precious stone beads, three-legged jar black, and redware pots with graffiti marks and shell objects. In 1964-65 S. R Rao has discovered first Neolithic site at Paiyampalli and conducted the excavation during the year 1964-65 and 1967-68 and brought to light two overlapping phases of Neolithic and Megalithic. The Palar River played a vital role in the archaeological settlements and cultural development of its inhabitants. The B. Narasimhaiah has discovered the Neolithic site and conducted Trail excavation at Chandrapuram in Tirupatur Taluk (1980).

V. PRESENT EXPLORATION

Systematic exploration was carried out by the present author to understand the material culture and cultural sequence of the village. Archaeological exploration revealed a large habitation mound, which is a mixture of sandy silty deposits measuring 3 m. above the surface level, and the extent of this habitation mound is more than two hectares. The Government of Tamil Nadu has cut the archaeological mound to store rainwater, clearly showing the archaeological cultural strata of different periods within a depth of 1 m. The Initial screening of this mound yielded cultural materials ranging from the Middle Paleolithic to the historical period. Some lithics were found at the site, namely complete flakes (Fig. 4), broken flakes (Fig. 5) Hammer Stone (Fig. 6), composed of quartzite. The pottery consisted of black-and-red ware, black ware, and graffiti potsherds (Fig. 7) painted ware (Fig. 8) Red Slipped ware, russet-coated painted ware, imitating a variety of Amphore, and a Coarse variety of red ware, in addition to ceramics, large amounts of antiquities were collected from broken terracotta figurines, hopscotch (Fig. 9), spout (Fig. 10), lid knob (Fig. 11). A few beads were collected from different raw materials, namely terracotta, glass, and ivory. A large number of iron slags and brickbats were observed at the site.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the present exploration and initial analysis of cultural material, such as lithic artifacts and potsherds, it is amply evident that this site was first occupied by the Middle Paleolithic period, when our ancestors used flake tools and hammer stones that were made out of quartzite. Meanwhile, the site was inhabited by the Iron Age and Early Historical people based on potsherds like Russet Coated painted ware, Black-and-Red ware, All Black ware, Red Slipped ware, Redware and a few graffiti-marked potsherds indicate the antiquity of this village of Kavur, Chengalpattu District can be dated back to Middle Palaeolithic and later was inhabited by the people of Iron Age and Early Historic people and then by Historical period. Further, investigations are required to understand the archaeological importance of the region

conducting the archaeological excavations at this site could reveal many important aspects related to our ancestors starting from the Middle Palaeolithic period to the Historical period.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I am indebted to thank my supervisor Prof. S. Rama Krishna Pisipaty, Department of Sanskrit & Indian Culture, Kanchipuram for his valuable time and guidance throughout this paper. A special thanks to my fellow friends M. Prasana, Dr. R. Ramesh, Assistant Archaeologist, Archaeological Survey of India, Chennai who helped me in the fieldwork and documentation. I am indebted thank the people of Kavur Village for their cooperation in every stage of in the field work.

Antiquities

Fig. 4: Flake tool

Fig. 5: Flake tool

Fig. 6: Pounder / Hammer stone

Fig. 7: Black and Red ware with Graffiti marks

Fig. 8: Painted Black and ware

Fig. 9: Hop Scotch

Fig. 10: Lid Knob

Fig. 11: Spoute

REFERENCES

1. Rajan, K. *Archaeology of Palar basin*, 2000.
2. Ramaswami, A., *Madras District Gazetteers*, Salem, Govt.Press, Madras, 1967.
3. Robert B.Foote, *The Foote Collection of Indian Prehistoric and Protohistoric Antiquities - Notes on their Ages and Distribution*, pt.2, Madras, 1916.
4. Krishnaswami, V.D., Stone Age India, *Ancient India*, vol.3, 1947, pp.11-57.
5. Sankalai, H.D., *Prehistory and Protohistory of India and Pakistan*, Poona, 1974, p.33.
6. *Indian Archaeology - A Review*, 1963-64, p.19.
7. Nardsimhaiah, B., *Neolithic and Megalithic Cultures in Tamil Nadu*, New Delhi, 1980, p.21.
8. Ghosh, A., *Encyclopaedia of Indian Archaeology*, vol.2, New Delhi, 1989.